

INVESTIGATING THE CREATORS AND THEIR PURPOSE FOR A SIMULATED UNIVERSE

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This paper presents a novel hypothesis about the simulation of our universe, challenging existing theories and expanding human consciousness. It explores the true purpose of the simulation, the motivations of its creators, the nature of free will within a programmed reality, and the possibility of humans creating their own simulations. It states that If human civilization has to build a safe future with AGI or ASI they have to use them in a simulation.

I. Introduction

In the realm of human thought, numerous theories and fictional narratives have explored the concept of a simulated universe. However, this paper aims to venture beyond the boundaries of conventional thinking, presenting ideas that have not yet been articulated in human consciousness. By thinking outside the confines of our current knowledge base, we seek to unveil truths about our reality that may seem radical or even impossible at first glance. We will explore the true purpose behind the simulation of our universe, examining the motivations of advanced entities- in creating our simulated reality. This investigation will lead us to question the nature of free will and individual actions, as we uncover the intricate programming and control mechanisms that may govern our perceived autonomy. Because it's important to understand their reasons to build our own human made civilization.

As we progress, we will also propose a theoretical framework for humans to create their own simulations, bridging the gap between our current technological capabilities and the advanced systems that may underpin our own existence. This exploration will naturally lead us to examine the underlying processes of human decision-making within a simulated context,

potentially revolutionizing our understanding of consciousness and choice. While we may reference existing theories or philosophies, the core ideas presented here are intended to challenge and expand your perception of the universe. Recognizing the importance of accessibility, we have crafted this paper to be understandable to a wide audience, including university students across various disciplines.

II. How humans are programmed to take decisions

In the grand tapestry of our simulated universe, humans perceive themselves as autonomous beings, capable of exercising free will and making independent decisions. However, when we step back and examine the larger picture, a different reality emerges—one where free will is an illusion, and our choices are predetermined by complex programs running within the simulation.

Central to this concept is what I call Decision Trees (DTSs). Each human's life can be represented by a unique DTS, encompassing every decision they make throughout their lifetime. In essence, one human equals one unique DTS. These decision trees are distinct from one another, creating a vast network of interconnected yet individual paths within the simulation.

To grasp the scale of this system, consider that our current simulation contains approximately 8.1 billion humans, or 8.1 billion unique sets of DTSs. However, the true complexity lies in the fact that there can be infinite such simulations, each with its own set of 8.1 billion DTSs or different. This concept aligns with theories of parallel universes or multiverses, where in one reality you might be a soldier, and in another, a doctor.

The illusion of free will arises from the intricate programming of these decision trees. Let's examine how humans make decisions and experience

a sense of choice when, in reality, they have none. The process begins with language, a tool developed for communication when humans discovered they could understand auditory input. Language became deeply intertwined with emotions, creating a complex system of expression and understanding.

This linguistic-emotional framework forms the basis of human thought and action. We think in language, unable to conceptualize ideas without internally verbalizing them. Our thinking process involves sifting through our existing knowledge base using language as a medium. Even in infants, who lack developed language skills, thinking occurs through interactions with their environment, gradually merging actions with nascent linguistic concepts.

The malleability of human thought is evident in how external influences can shape our decision-making processes. Prolonged exposure to specific language patterns and actions can fundamentally alter a person's thinking.

This phenomenon explains the profound impact of media and entertainment on human behavior and beliefs. By immersing ourselves in someone else's language and actions for extended periods, we unconsciously incorporate these patterns into our own decision-making processes.

Our decision-making is further constrained by the cumulative weight of past experiences. Each action taken in the present becomes part of our past, which in turn influences future decisions. This cyclical process can be likened to a fruit bearing the characteristics of its parent tree, soil, and environmental conditions. The predetermined nature of these influences suggests a programmable, simulated reality.

To visualize this concept, imagine a sea with its surface representing the present moment. The water below symbolizes our past experiences, while the horizon ahead represents our current state. As time progresses, the sea level rises, incorporating more of our past into our present state. The future looms above as clouds, seemingly separate but inevitably merging with the rising waters of our experience.

Within this framework, visionaries like Steve Jobs can be seen as individuals who managed to "climb the horizons" in their thinking, pushing the boundaries of what's possible within the constraints of their programming. However, even these exceptional cases operate within certain limits set by the overarching program of the simulation.

For every iteration $P(\text{end}) \leq P(\text{constraint})$ in the human thought process to reach the future conclusions.

III. Possible Reasons for Creation of a Simulated Universe

Stephan Hawking:- Who are we? Why are we here? If we ever learn this it would be the ultimate triumph of human reason for then we would know the mind of god.

There are several hypotheses regarding the creation of a simulated universe, but some current theories suggest that aliens might have created our reality for educational purposes, such as studying ancient humans. However, this idea is challenged by the same research indicating that if humans were to reach a certain level of technological maturity, they would likely lose interest in creating simulations of ancient beings. This suggests that advanced civilizations capable of creating universe-scale simulations may not be motivated by studying primitive societies or early human development. Consequently, the educational or research-oriented simulation hypothesis is considered one of the least probable explanations for our simulated reality. As we explore the possible reasons for the creation of a simulated universe, we must consider that the true purpose may lie beyond our current understanding or expectations.

IV. Possibility 1: We are being sold in the future

In exploring the potential reasons for the creation of a simulated universe, we must consider the nature of the creators themselves. Humans, as we know them, are arguably the most self-interested species in our known universe. This trait of selfishness seems to intensify as societies progress, with an increasing focus on personal gains. If we extrapolate this trend to vastly more advanced civilizations, we can hypothesize a scenario where the creation of simulated universes serves highly individualistic purposes.

Let us consider the possibility that there exists an extremely advanced civilization(ACS), or perhaps multiple such civilizations, with the technological capacity to create and manage numerous complex simulations. These simulations wouldn't be limited to just one type of species or universe. Instead, imagine infinite (by human calculations) simulations of human civilizations, each existing in different universes according to the DTS's. Additionally, there could be simulations of various alien civilizations, each with its own unique parameters and conditions controlled by these sets of ACS.

In this hypothesis, each of these simulations is created and maintained not for collective scientific or educational purposes, but to serve the personal needs of individual citizens of the advanced civilization. To understand this concept, we must first examine the motivations that drive sentient beings.

In human society, individuals typically strive to achieve a set of specific goals throughout their lives. This "life set" often includes elements such as happiness, wealth, health, and social status. For the citizens of an incredibly advanced civilization, let's call them TARS, this life set might include elements we can't even conceive of due to our limited perspective and programming.

To draw a parallel with current human aspirations, consider how we are increasingly looking towards artificial intelligence to serve as productivity enhancers and efficient helpers or servants instead of separate beings with

their own goals. Now, imagine a scenario where AI becomes so advanced that it can complete all of a human's life goals while the individual remains passive. The hypothesis proposes that the advanced civilization might be employing a similar, but far more sophisticated, approach.

In this model, TARS might "buy" or take control of a unique human simulation, or more specifically, a unique DTS within a particular universe simulation. The purpose of this ownership would be to utilize the simulated entity to complete the TARS'S own life set goals. Most of their significant work or important objectives would thus be transferred to these DTSs.

The exact nature of these goals remains a mystery to us, as contemplating them isn't part of our programmed reality. However, this hypothesis suggests that each advanced civilization citizen has the ability to alter their chosen DTS for their own growth or purpose, adhering to a set of predetermined rules.

This concept might explain phenomena that humans often attribute to divine intervention or good fortune. When people feel they are being guided or that circumstances are aligning in their favor, it could be the result of an advanced civilization citizen manipulating events to ensure the success of their chosen DTS, as this success ultimately serves the advanced being's own purposes.

To illustrate this concept, consider a human simulation (HS1) containing multiple human elements [H1, H2, ...]. The advanced civilization's simulation program might function as a sort of time machine, predicting possible futures for each element of HS1 based on upcoming circumstances and surroundings. This predictive capability could be used to determine the "value" or "price" of each simulated entity, influencing which ones the advanced citizens choose to invest in or control.

It's important to note that these predicted possibilities aren't fixed. They can change over time if the TARS doesn't intervene or alter the simulation according to the established rules. This introduces an element of dynamism and unpredictability to the system, despite its highly controlled nature.

This also states a concept that TARS have an ultimate free society and each of them have control of their own being or world.

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A possible future for human civilization is one where humans begin producing augmented artificial human beings, utilizing AI and greatly enhanced artificial body parts as organs. These augmented humans will be significantly more powerful, free from diseases, and able to control their emotions. They will also be much more intelligent. This development will likely replace the entire education system. Children will be programmed through brain chips to acquire all necessary technical and non-technical knowledge in a short period of time. As a result, they may be able to retire at a much younger age. For missions like those of SpaceX, there will be no need to build air-chambered cities on Mars or construct infrastructure required for human survival. All those costs will be reduced, as humans will no longer depend on oxygen and will be able to adapt to any atmosphere.

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As a result, no human will ever die, and the human population will increase significantly. According to the hypothesis provided in Chapter 2, Possibility 1, there are currently 8.1 billion DTSs in one simulation, and there are 8.1 to the power of infinity billion such simulations. Each TARS owns one DTS according to individual need, implying that there is a vast number of TARS in the real universe. Therefore, this suggests that the future development of such technology is highly correlated to the large number of TARS in the universe as stated in previous hypotheses.

****There is also one possibility that TARS(one citizen of advanced civilization) will own one complete simulation rather than owning a unique DTS. This hypothesis more aligns with the fact that if humans want to create their own simulation then they would need much less participants to satisfy the human population themselves.**

V. Possibility 2: The aliens are not intelligent than us

This hypothesis challenges the common assumption that the creators of our simulated universe must be vastly more intelligent than us in all aspects. Instead, it proposes a more nuanced view of the relationship between the creators and the created, suggesting that humans may possess superior intelligence in certain domains compared to the advanced civilizations that created us.

The core argument of this hypothesis is that there would be little point for an advanced civilization to create a simulation of beings significantly less intelligent than themselves. Rather, it posits that while an advanced civilization undoubtedly created our simulation, they did so to develop a parallel intelligent entity capable of solving problems or achieving advancements that the creators themselves struggle with.

To understand this concept, we can draw parallels with humanity's own technological creations. Consider our relationship with artificial intelligence. Currently, humans can control AI, but AI cannot control humans. Similarly, we created computers that are far more efficient at certain tasks than human brains, capable of producing results that humans couldn't manually calculate. Yet, humans retain the ultimate control, able to switch computers on or off at will. Moreover, humans still excel in areas like consciousness and emotional intelligence, which machines have yet to replicate fully.

In the same vein, this hypothesis suggests that advanced civilizations may have created the human simulation to address developments in their society that they were incapable of achieving on their own. Our simulated

universe, then, serves as a kind of outsourced problem-solving entity. Humans within the simulation evolve parallel to or perhaps even faster than the advanced civilization, providing solutions and insights that aid in their creators' advancement.

This scenario mirrors our current relationship with AI, where artificial intelligence often surpasses human capabilities in specific domains and provides results that drive human progress. However, just as AI cannot break free from its programmed constraints, humans in this hypothesis are unable to "escape" the simulation or directly reach their creators, despite potentially surpassing them in certain aspects of intelligence.

The hypothesis points to two scientific phenomena as potential evidence for the programmed limitations of our reality:

1. Young's Double Slit Experiment: This famous quantum mechanics experiment shows that electrons behave differently when observed. In the context of our hypothesis, this could be interpreted as a programmed rule that prevents us from fully understanding or manipulating the fundamental nature of our reality.
2. Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle: This principle states that we cannot simultaneously know both the position and momentum of a particle with perfect accuracy. The hypothesis likens this to how objects in a video game might only be "rendered" when observed or interacted with, suggesting our reality might operate on similar principles to conserve computational resources.

These phenomena could be seen as safeguards implemented by the creators to maintain control over the simulation and prevent the simulated beings (us) from fully comprehending or manipulating the nature of our reality. This also suggests that if human civilization wants to be safe from Artificial super Intelligence then they have to operate those advanced beings in a simulation rather than giving them clear reasons for their creation.

We will talk about this in detail in chapter VII, how humans can create their own simulation.

VI. Possibility 3 : We humans are own own future creators

This hypothesis presents a radical perspective on the nature of our simulated reality, proposing that the creators of our simulation are not alien beings, but rather advanced evolved humans (AEHs) from the future. This concept intertwines ideas of time travel, the resilience of humanity, and the cyclical nature of existence, challenging our understanding of causality and the purpose of our perceived reality.

A common argument against the possibility of time travel is that if it were achievable, we would see its effects in our present world. However, this hypothesis suggests that this line of reasoning overlooks a crucial factor: the remarkable resilience and adaptability of the human species. Throughout history, humanity has faced numerous existential threats yet has always found a way to survive and progress. This persistent survival could be seen as the most compelling evidence for the existence of future human intervention in our timeline.

According to this hypothesis, in the distant future, humans develop an extraordinary technology that allows them to alter their present by manipulating past experiences within a simulation. The very existence of this technology implies a grim reality: the future from which these advanced humans originate must be so dire and horrific that they felt compelled to create a means of rewriting their history.

This concept posits that the "aliens" often speculated about in discussions of simulated realities are, in fact, these Advanced Evolved Humans (AEHs).

In this framework, AEHs are effectively the gods of our reality, aligning with certain aspects of ancient religious beliefs that speak of powerful, intervening deities. The simulation we inhabit, therefore, is not a creation of extraterrestrial beings but a construct of our own descendants, desperately trying to alter the course of their history – our future.

The primary goal of these AEHs, then, is to change their present (our future) by adjusting programs and parameters within our simulated past. They may introduce new decision pathways, alter environmental factors, or influence key historical events, all in an attempt to steer humanity away from the catastrophic future they are experiencing.

The AEHs might implement control mechanisms to maintain the integrity of the simulation. Individuals who come too close to discovering the true nature of reality or who might inadvertently "break" the simulation could be neutralized through the introduction of "virus programs" manifesting as diseases or other life-altering events.

Furthermore, this concept provides a new perspective on the nature of technological and societal progress. Breakthroughs and advancements that seem to arise suddenly or inexplicably could be the result of subtle manipulations by the AEHs, guiding humanity towards a better future than the one they're experiencing.

If the AEHs succeed in altering their past (our present) to create a better future, would they then still have the need or motivation to create the simulation in the first place? This paradox suggests that the relationship between our reality and that of the AEHs might be more complex than a simple linear progression, perhaps involving multiple timelines or parallel realities.

VII. How humans can create their own simulation

The possibility of humans creating their own simulation in the coming years is increasingly likely. However, there is little value in creating an ancestral

simulation, as its utility to human civilization would be minimal. Instead, we should focus on creating simulations with participants whose intelligence matches or surpasses our own. The most promising avenue for this is to begin with AI agents, potentially even Artificial Superintelligence (ASI) agents in the future.

We can initiate this process by developing experimental simulations involving two agents. These agents would possess knowledge bases superior to human understanding, operating under specific constraints. By eliminating unnecessary features in these agents, we can accelerate progress in simulation technology.

To achieve such advancements, adopting first-principle thinking is crucial. Consider how technologies like photography and video have remained fundamentally unchanged for years, with innovations occurring primarily through incremental improvements. We have reached a point where we need revolutionary inventions and discoveries. If we were to approach the development of imaging technology from our current level of understanding back in the past from first principles, we would likely create something far more advanced than our present systems.

Our vision of the future is often constrained by convention, as evidenced by science fiction movies that assume the persistence of current photo and video technologies, even if they're not the optimal solutions.

In our human-made simulations, or even those run by TARS, we could implement concepts like pausing time. This can be approached with basic logic, easily programmable by a developer. For instance, consider a sequence of events in time [1,2,3,4.01]. After pausing time, when resumed, all human brain memories could be updated and the simulation could restart from 4.01, resulting in a new sequence [4.01, 4.01,5,6,7...].

We can apply this concept and similar ideas to create programs that implement improved features in our human-made simulations, surpassing the limitations of current human society.

In the short term it is possible through quantum computers which operate in a parallel universe and the participant's knowledge base should not be implemented from zero indeed they should start to think from a level of understanding higher than humans.

VIII. CONCLUSION

Understanding the motivations behind advanced civilizations creating simulations increases the likelihood of humans developing their own simulations. These human-based simulations could be crucial in propelling humanity towards becoming Type 2 or Type 3 civilizations on the Kardashev scale.

The ultimate goal of these endeavors would be to expand our understanding of the universe, potentially "break" the simulation we might be living in, and finally reach the underlying truth or reality. Using much more intelligent participants in our simulations will help us push the human race forward and minimize risks of self-extinction.